

Impact Factor: 4.9

ISSN: 2181-0664

DOI: 10.26739/2181-0664

www.tadqiqot.uz

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

Volume 4, Issue 1

2023

ISSN 2181-0664

Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-0664

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

4 ЖИЛД, 1 СОН

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ

ТОМ 4, НОМЕР 1

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 1

ТОШКЕНТ-2023

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ | UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

№1 (2023) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-0664-2023-1>

Бош мухаррир:
Главный редактор:
Chief Editor:

Мадазимов Мадамин Муминович
Ректор Андижанского Государственного
медицинского института, д.м.н., профессор
кафедры факультетской и госпитальной
хирургии

Тахририят раиси:
Председатель редакционной коллегии:
Chairman of the editorial Board:

Алексеев Андрей Анатольевич
Директор ожогового центра НМИЦ хирургии
им. В.Вишневского, главный комбустиолог
Министерства здравоохранения России, д.м.н.,
профессор.

Бош мухаррир ўринбосари:
Заместитель главного редактора:
Deputy Chief Editor:

Салахиддинов Камалиддин Зухриддинович
доцент, д.м.н. кафедры факультетской и
госпитальной хирургии Андижанского
Государственного медицинского института

Бош мухаррир ўринбосари:
Заместитель главного редактора:
Deputy Chief Editor:

Хегай Любовь Николаевна
доцент, к.м.н., начальник отдела по координации
деятельности грантов Межвузовской научно-
исследовательской лаборатории Ташкентской
медицинской академии

Маъсул котиб:
Ответственный секретарь:
Executive Secretary:

Досина Маргарита Олеговна
в.н.с. ГНУ "Институт физиологии Национальной
академии наук Беларуси", к.б.н., председатель
Совета молодых ученых Отделения медицинских
наук НАН Беларуси

Маъсул котиб:
Ответственный секретарь:
Executive Secretary:

Ниязова Зебинисо Анваровна
PhD кафедры офтальмологии, детской
офтальмологии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ ТАХРИРИЙ МАСЛАХАТ КЕНГАШИ | РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ EDITORIAL BOARD OF THE UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

Хужамбердиев Мамазоир Ахмедович

д.м.н., профессор кафедры госпитальной терапии Андижанского Государственного медицинского института

Привалова Ирина Леонидовна

д.б.н., профессор кафедры нормальной физиологии Курского государственного медицинского университета,
заведующая лабораторией физиологии висцеральных систем НИИ физиологии (Курск)

Гаврилова Елена Анатольевна

д.м.н., профессор, заведующая кафедрой лечебной физкультуры и спортивной медицины Северо-западного
государственного медицинского университета им. И.И. Мечникова (Санкт-Петербург)

Чурганов Олег Анатольевич

д.п.н., профессор кафедры ЛФК и спортивной медицины Северо-Западного государственного
медицинского университета им. И.И. Мечникова (Санкт-Петербург)

Салахиддинов Зухриддин Салахиддинович

д.м.н., профессор, заведующий кафедры ВОП №1, Андижанского государственного медицинского института

Рябчиков Денис Анатольевич

д.м.н., в.н.с. онкологического отделения хирургических методов лечения ФГБУ "НМИЦ
онкологии им. Н.Н. Блохина" Минздрава России

Гулямов Суръат Саидвалиевич

д.м.н., профессор кафедры оториноларингологии, детской оториноларингологии, стоматологии
Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Тереза Магалхайз
профессор, заведующая кафедрой Судебной медицины государственного университета Порту (Португалия)

Юлдашев Илхом Рузиевич
д.м.н., профессор, заведующий кафедрой Аллергологии, иммунологии, микробиологии
Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Хамраев Абдурашид Журакулович
д.м.н., профессор кафедры госпитальной детской хирургии, Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

РЕДАКЦИОННАЯ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Эрматов Низом Жумакулович
д.м.н., доцент, заведующий кафедрой гигиены детей и подростков и гигиены питания Ташкентской медицинской академии

Рузиев Шерзод Ибодуллаевич
д.м.н., доцент кафедры судебной медицины и медицинского права Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Якубова Олтиной Абдуганиевна
доктор медицинских наук, доцент, заведующая кафедрой акушерства и гинекологии, неонатологии факультета повышения квалификации и переподготовки врачей Андижанского государственного медицинского института

Бабич Светлана Михайловна
доцент, заведующая кафедрой социальной гигиены Андижанского государственного медицинского института

Сабирова Рихси Абдукадировна
д.м.н., профессор кафедры медицинской и биологической химии Ташкентской медицинской академии

Цеомашко Наталья Евгеньевна
д.б.н. с.н.с., заведующая отделом медико-генетических исследований МНИЛ Ташкентской медицинской академии

Хамраева Лола Салимовна
доцент, к.м.н. кафедры офтальмологии, детской офтальмологии Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Усманходжаева Адиба Амирсайдовна
доцент, к.м.н., заведующая кафедрой Народной медицины, реабилитологии и физической культуры Ташкентской медицинской академии

Тухтаева Нигора Хасановна
DSc, доцент кафедры пропедевтики внутренних болезней № 2, Ташкентской медицинской академии.

Шарипова Фарида Камильевна
к.м.н., доцент кафедры психиатрии, наркологии и детской психиатрии, медицинской психологии, психотерапии
Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Бузруков Батир Тулкунович
д.м.н., профессор, заведующий кафедрой офтальмологии, детской офтальмологии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

Туйчиев Галибжан Урмонжонович
к.м.н., доцент, заведующий кафедрой детской хирургии, детской анестезиологии-реаниматологии с курсом
офтальмологии и стоматологии факультета усовершенствования и переподготовки врачей АГМИ

Маматхужаева Гулнора Нажмитдиновна
доцент, к.м.н. кафедры Офтальмологии Андижанского Государственного медицинского института

Каримова Зиёда Кушбаевна
доцент, к.м.н. кафедры Аллергологии, клинической иммунологии, микробиологии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

Саидходжаева Саида Набиевна
доцент, PhD кафедры неврологии, детской неврологии и медицинской генетики Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

Зуфарова Зухра Хабибуллаевна
доцент, к.ф.н. кафедры промышленной технологии лекарственных средств Ташкентского фармацевтического института

Алимова Дурдона Дильмуратовна
PhD кафедры оториноларингологии, детской оториноларингологии, детской стоматологии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

Page Maker | Верстка | Саҳифаловчи: Хўршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

1. Inoyatov A.Sh., Saidova M.A. MICROCIRCULATORY DISTURBANCES IN PATIENTS WITH POST-COVID SYNDROME AND TROPHIC ULCERS OF THE MUCOSUS MEMBRANE OF THE ORAL CAVITY.....	6
2. Ibragimova M.Kh., Juraeva S.R. THE ROLE OF CHOLISAL IN THE COMPLEX TREATMENT OF PERIODONTAL AND ORAL MUCOSA DISEASES.....	11
3. Ibragimova M.Kh., Omonova Sh.F., Nomurodova F.L., Normurodova A.K. ASSESSMENT OF THE MICROBIOLOGICAL STATUS OF CHRONIC CATARRHAL GINGIVITIS IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC HEPATITIS.....	14
4. Fozilov M.M., Bekmurov B.G., Xaydarov B.X., Saitnazarov J.E., Cho'liyev O.O. PREVENTION OF ALVEOLAR RIDGE ATROPHY AND DEFORMATIES AFTER TOOTH EXTRACTION. (An article review).....	19
5. Mukhsinova M.Kh., Raimkulova D.F. CLINICAL AND DIAGNOSTIC FEATURES AND METHODS OF MODERN THERAPY OF ACUTE OBSTRUCTIVE BRONCHITIS IN CHILDREN.....	24
6. Khushmurodova M.A., Madjidova Y.N., Samatov F., Urakova U. ASSESSMENT OF PSYCHOMOTOR DEVELOPMENT IN INFANTS WITH BILIRUBIN-INDUCED NEUROLOGICAL DYSFUNCTION.....	30
7. Tursunkulova D.A. MODERN METHODS OF NEBULIZER THERAPY FOR ACUTE BRONCHOO- OBSTRUCTIVE SYNDROME IN CHILDREN.....	37
8. Shavazi Nurali Mamedovich, Tursunkulova Dilshoda Akmalovna INFLUENCE OF RISK FACTORS ON THE COURSE OF OBSTRUCTIVE BRONCHITIS ON THE BACKGROUND OF ENCEPHALOPATHY IN YOUNG CHILDREN.....	41
9. Yuldasheva N.A., Kamilov Kh.P. LABORATORY RESEARCH PREGNANT WOMEN WITH HERPETIC STOMATITIS.....	45
10. Halimov A.A., Tulaboeva G.M., Sagatova H.M., Abdukadirova N.M., Muminov S.D. CHRONIC HEART FAILURE AND LIVER DYSFUNCTION (Literature review).....	50

ISSN: 2181-0664

www.tadqiqot.uz

Ibragimova M.Kh.,
Omonova Sh.F.,
Nomurodova F.L.,
Normurodova A.K.

Tashkent State Dental Institute,
Department of hospital therapeutic stomatology
e-mail: leylafarxadovna1997@gmail.com

ASSESSMENT OF THE MICROBIOLOGICAL STATUS OF CHRONIC CATARRHAL GINGIVITIS IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC HEPATITIS

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7582002>

ABSTRACT

It has now been proven that periodontopathogens of dental plaque are the etiological factor of inflammatory lesions of the periodontium. Modern studies show that *A. actinomycetemcomitans* plays a significant role in the development of rapidly progressive periodontitis, the content of this microorganism directly correlates with the size of the periodontal pocket and the severity of inflammatory and destructive changes in the periodontium. However, a number of authors express doubts about the etiological role of these bacteria in the development of inflammatory periodontal diseases. The interpretation of the results of the microbiological study of the materials was carried out taking into account the differential signs formed during the growth of colonies, characteristic of each type of bacteria.

Keywords: microbiology, etiology, inflammatory process, bacteria, periodontal, microorganism, periodontal pocket, destructive change, dental plaque, pathogenic microorganism.

Ибрагимова М.Х.,
Омонова Ш.Ф.,
Номуродова Ф.Л.,
Номуродова А.К.

Ташкентский государственный стоматологический
Институт кафедры госпитальной терапевтической стоматологии
e-mail: leylafarxadovna1997@gmail.com

ОЦЕНКА МИКРОБИОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО СТАТУСА ХРОНИЧЕСКОГО КАТАРАЛЬНОГО ГИНГИВИТА У БОЛЬНЫХ ХРОНИЧЕСКИМ ГЕПАТИТОМ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В настоящее время доказано, что этиологическим фактором воспалительных поражений пародонта являются пародонтопатогены зубной бляшки. Современные исследования демонстрируют, что *A. actinomycetemcomitans* играет существенную роль в

развитии быстро прогрессирующего пародонтита, содержание этого микроорганизма напрямую коррелирует с величиной пародонтального кармана и со степенью тяжести воспалительно-деструктивных изменений в пародонте. Однако, ряд авторов высказывает сомнение относительно этиологической роли данных бактерий в развитии воспалительных заболеваний пародонта. Интерпретацию полученных результатов микробиологического исследования материалов проводили, учитывая дифференциальные признаки, образовавшихся в ходе роста колоний, характерные для каждого вида бактерий.

Ключевые слова: микробиология, этиология, воспалительный процесс, бактерия, пародонт, микроорганизм, пародонтальный карман, деструктивные изменения, зубной бляшки, патогенный микроорганизм.

**Ibragimova M.X.,
Omonova Sh.F.,
Nomurodova F.L.,
Normurodova A.Q.**

Toshkent Davlat Stomatologiya Instituti,
gospital terapevtik stomatologiya kafedrası
e-mail: leylafarxadovna1997@gmail.com

SURUNKALI GEPATIT BILAN OG'RIGAN BEMORLARDA SURUNKALI KATARAL GINGIVITNING MIKROBIOLOGIK HOLATINI BAHOLASH

ANNOTATSIYA

Hozirgi vaqtda tish blyashka periodontopatogenlari periodontning yallig'lanishli lezyonlarining etiologik omili ekanligi isbotlangan. Zamonaviy tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, *A. actinomycetemcomitans* tez progressiv periodontitning rivojlanishida muhim rol o'ynaydi, bu mikroorganizmning tarkibi periodontal cho'ntakning kattaligi va periodontidagi yallig'lanish va destruktiv o'zgarishlarning og'irligi bilan bevosita bog'liq. Biroq, bir qator mualliflar bu bakteriyalarning yallig'lanishli periodontal kasalliklarning rivojlanishidagi etiologik rolga shubha bildiradilar. Materiallarni mикробиологик o'rganish natijalarini talqin qilish har bir bakteriya turiga xos bo'lgan koloniyalarning o'sishi jarayonida hosil bo'lgan differentsial belgilarni hisobga olgan holda amalga oshirildi.

Kalit so'zlar: mикробиологiya, etiologiya, yallig'lanish jarayoni, bakteriya, parodont, mikroorganizm, parodontal cho'ntak, destruktiv o'zgarish, tish blyashkasi, patogen mikroorganizm.

Introduction. It has now been proven that periodontopathogens of dental plaque are the etiological factor of inflammatory lesions of the periodontium. Modern studies show that *A. actinomycetemcomitans* plays a significant role in the development of rapidly progressive periodontitis, the content of this microorganism directly correlates with the size of the periodontal pocket and the severity of inflammatory and destructive changes in the periodontium. However, a number of authors express doubts about the etiological role of these bacteria in the development of inflammatory periodontal diseases. [1,2] The interpretation of the results of the microbiological study of the materials was carried out taking into account the differential signs formed during the growth of colonies, characteristic of each type of bacteria.

Staphylococci are characterized by golden (*S. aureus*) or white (*S. epidermidis*, *S. saprophyticus*) colonies. In micrococci, colonies are usually colored yellow (with various shades - from yellow-green to orange) or pink (up to red). The vast majority of *S. aureus* strains and some strains of *S. epidermidis* dissolve erythrocytes, forming a transparent zone of hemolysis around the colonies. Micrococci do not possess hemolytic proper. [3,5,7,8]

Streptococci differentiate among themselves by the type of hemolysis on blood agar, which is due to the lysis of red blood cells. In this case, a transparent zone is formed around the colonies, up to complete enlightenment of the medium with a width from tenths to several millimeters. Colonies

of β -hemolytic streptococci can be: mucoid with a diameter of 1.5-2.5 mm, regular round shape, resembling dew drops in their appearance; rough, 1.5-2.5 mm in diameter, round colonies, grayish white, with a characteristic slightly raised center; smooth, small, 1-1.5 mm in diameter, spherical colonies with a smooth edge, with a shiny moist surface.[9,10,11,12] α -hemolytic or greenish streptococci form an α -reaction on blood agar in the form of a translucent, greenish tint zone, and the formation of small colonies, 1-1.5 mm in diameter, grayish-greenish in color with a smooth or rough surface. γ - streptococci are inert towards erythrocytes and hemoglobin; they do not change the appearance of blood agar and are called non-hemolytic [2,4,13].

Objective: To assess the microbiological status of chronic catarrhal gingivitis in patients with chronic hepatitis.

Materials and methods. For microbiological examination in patients with chronic catarrhal gingivitis, the following material was taken:

- oral fluid, by spitting, was collected in sterile vials in the amount of 1 ml, which were closed with a sterile cap, the contents of the periodontal sulcus were taken on a sterile, hygroscopic cotton wick on a dental probe and also dipped into a sterile vial with 1 ml of saline, closed with a sterile cap. Isolation of microorganisms from their natural habitat - tissues and fluids of the oral cavity - was carried out by sowing the studied materials on artificial nutrient media. The method we use is called culture research. Sowing on nutrient media of the test material was carried out by taking 0.1 ml of oral fluid and 0.1 ml from the vial, which contained saline and the contents of the periodontal sulcus.

Sowing on nutrient media of the test material was carried out by taking 0.1 ml of oral fluid and 0.1 ml from the vial, which contained saline and the contents of the periodontal sulcus.

Primary inoculation of the material for the study was carried out on a dense nutrient medium in Petri dishes. After picking up the material in a pipette, and opening the cup, one drop was applied to the medium and rubbed with a spatula over the entire surface of the agar.

To isolate the general microflora, inoculation was carried out on blood agar, which was prepared as follows. To the nutrient agar melted and cooled to 45-50°C (pH 7.4-7.6) add 5-10% defibrinated or fresh whole blood of an animal (sheep, rabbit, cattle) or human blood waste, the latter is preliminarily checked for sterility sowing on sugar broth, which is left for 18-20 hours in a thermostat. Agar with blood is thoroughly mixed, avoiding the formation of foam, and poured into cups with a layer of 3-4 mm. Cultivation is carried out in a thermostat at a temperature of 37°C, for 18-20 hours. Endo's medium was used to detect intestinal microflora.

For its manufacture, 100 ml of ordinary agar (pH 7.4) is melted in a water bath or in a fluid steam apparatus, cooled to 70°C and 1 g of chemically pure lactose is added, previously dissolved in a sterile test tube in a small amount of distilled water and boiled

In separate test tubes, prepare: 1) 2-3 ml of an alcoholic saturated solution of basic fuchsin, 2) 10 ml of a 10% aqueous solution of sodium sulfite (Na_2SO_3). 1 ml of fuchsin solution is measured into a sterile test tube and sodium sulfite solution is added until the fuchsin discolors (pale pink color). The prepared mixture is poured into the melted agar, mixed well, avoiding the formation of foam, and poured into cups with a layer of 3-4 mm. Hot agar has a pale pink color, when solidified it becomes colorless. Cultivation is carried out in a thermostat at a temperature of 37°C, for 18-20 hours. To detect fungi of the genus *Candida* in the test material, it was inoculated on Sabouraud's medium. The basis of this medium is yeast water. For 1 liter of tap (non-distilled) water, 80 g of pressed baker's yeast (or 20 g of dry yeast) are taken, boiled for 15 minutes, passed through a paper filter, poured into vials and sterilized at 1 atm. 20 minutes. To 100 ml of sterile yeast water add 1% peptone, 2% agar, heat until the agar dissolves, then add 4% glucose (or maltose), filter, pour into test tubes (pH 5.8) and sterilize at 0.5 atm. 20 minutes. After sterilization, the medium in the test tubes is slanted. Cultivation is carried out in a thermostat at a temperature of 37°C for 5 days.

The interpretation of the results of the microbiological study of the materials was carried out taking into account the differential signs formed during the growth of colonies, characteristic of each type of bacteria.

Staphylococci are characterized by golden (*S. aureus*) or white (*S. epidermidis*, *S. saprophyticus*) colonies. In micrococci, colonies are usually colored yellow (with various shades -

from yellow-green to orange) or pink (up to red). The vast majority of *S. aureus* strains and some strains of *S. epidermidis* dissolve erythrocytes, forming a transparent zone of hemolysis around the colonies. Micrococci do not possess hemolytic properties.

Streptococci differentiate among themselves by the type of hemolysis on blood agar, which is due to the lysis of red blood cells. In this case, a transparent zone is formed around the colonies, up to complete enlightenment of the medium with a width from tenths to several millimeters. Colonies of β -hemolytic streptococci can be: mucoid with a diameter of 1.5-2.5 mm, regular round shape, resembling dew drops in their appearance; rough, 1.5-2.5 mm in diameter, round colonies, grayish white, with a characteristic slightly raised center; smooth, small, 1-1.5 mm in diameter, spherical colonies with a smooth edge, with a shiny moist surface.

α -hemolytic or greenish streptococci form an α -reaction on blood agar in the form of a translucent, greenish tint zone, and the formation of small colonies, 1-1.5 mm in diameter, grayish-greenish in color with a smooth or rough surface. γ - streptococci are inert towards erythrocytes and hemoglobin; they do not change the appearance of blood agar and are called non-hemolytic

Neisseria grow on the surface of blood agar as round smooth colonies with even edges, a shiny surface or irregularly shaped rough colonies with jagged edges with a bizarre surface, some have a yellow pigment. Various species of *Moraxella* grow as large, translucent, round, moist, sometimes slimy colonies with little or no hemolysis. Microbes of the genus *Acinetobacter* grow in the form of large, white, round, shiny, often mucous colonies, possibly with a small area of hemolysis around

Colonies of *Corynebacterium* are round, opaque, oily small or large, creamy, pale yellow, orange-brown, smooth without hemolysis zones.

On the Endo medium, the colonies of representatives of the Enterobacteriaceae family are convex, with regular rounded outlines, more or less opalescent, sometimes mucous. They may be red with a metallic sheen, may be colorless, pinkish or greyish with a more or less pronounced dark center, especially in larger colonies.

Colonies of fungi of the genus *Candida* are convex, creamy, glossy, but not wet, smooth or slightly wrinkled, first white, then cream.

The number of grown colonies was counted on nutrient media from 0.1 ml of oral fluid and from 0.1 ml from a vial containing 1 ml of saline and the contents of the periodontal sulcus

Results. When conducting microbiological studies of the oral fluid and the contents of the periodontal sulcus, the following main types of microorganisms were found: streptococci, staphylococci, micrococci, *neisseria*, *Corynebacterium* species, *Enterodacter* species, *Pseudomonas* species, *Candida albicans*. The most common, 20% or more cases of detection, β -hemolytic streptococci, *Neisseria*, fungi *Candida albicans*.

Quantitative microbiological indicators of these microorganisms most significantly decreased after professional oral hygiene, similar to the indicators of clinical studies. Therefore, we analyzed the dynamics of the following microorganisms: β - hemolytic streptococci, *Neisseria*, *Candida albicans*. The average number of *Neisseria* colonies in moderate gingivitis is 4.6 times higher than in mild gingivitis, with an equal number of cases of detection of this type of microorganisms in the contents of the periodontal sulcus. The average number of *Candida albicans* colonies did not differ significantly in chronic catarrhal gingivitis of mild and moderate severity, with a higher frequency of detection in mild forms of gingivitis by 6.1 times. Quantitative microbiological indicators of microorganisms: streptococci, staphylococci, micrococci, *neisseria*, *Corynebacterium* species, *Enterodacter* species, *Pseudomonas* species, *Candida albicans*, most significantly decreased after professional oral hygiene, similar to clinical studies.

References.

1. Babenya A.A. Features of the manifestation of dental pathology in persons with diseases of the gastrointestinal tract (literature review) / A. A. Babenya // Innovation in dentistry. - 2015. - No. 1. -p.72-75.

2. Banchenko G.V., Maksimovsky Yu.M., Grinin V.M. The tongue is the mirror of the body. Clinical guide for physicians. - M., 2000. - 456 p.2.
3. Banchenko, G.V. Combined diseases of the oral mucosa and internal organs / G.V. Banchenko. - M., Medicine, 1979. - 190 p.]
4. Eremin O.V., Lepilin A.V., Kozlova I.V., Kargin D.V. Comorbidity of periodontal and gastrointestinal diseases // Saratov Journal of Medical Scientific Research. 2009. №3. –p.16-19
1. Zhazhkov E.N. Complex treatment of chronic catarrhal gingivitis and mild periodontitis with the use of argon plasma flow: Ph.D. dis. ... cand. honey. Sciences / E.N. Zhazhkov. - Smolensk, 2010. - 20 p.
2. Kamilov Kh.P., Ibragimova M.Kh. Features of the diagnosis of periodontal diseases in patients with chronic calculous cholecystitis // J. Biomedicine. - 2019. - No. 1. - pp. 60 - 68)
3. Kamilov Kh.P., Ibragimova M.Kh. Samadova Sh.I. The use of ozonized sesame oil in the complex treatment of erosive-ulcerative form of lichen planus of the oral mucosa//Medicine and innovation. - 2021.-№1.-pp. 83-92
4. Kuzmina, OV Pathology of the periodontium in chronic diffuse liver diseases / OV Kuzmina // Chronic diffuse liver diseases in general medical practice Textbook, approval for the publication of the UMO on medical and pharmaceutical education of Russian universities, Compilation IV Kozlova, MV Safonova-Saratov Izd - in SSMU, 2006 -pp. 100-107
5. Maksimovskaya L.N., Dzhamaldinova T.D., Sokolova M.A. The state of the microcirculation system of gum tissues in patients with inflammatory periodontal diseases against the background of various stages of GERD // Stomatology for everyone. 2011. No. 1.- pp. 14-17.
11. Morozova, S.I. Diseases of the oral mucosa: Atlas / S.I. Morozova, N.A. Savelyeva - M.: LLC "Medical Information Agency", 2012. - 272 p.: ill.].
6. Moseeva M.V., Khokhlacheva N.A. Dental complaints of patients with erosive and ulcerative lesions of the gastroduodenal zone // Vyatskiy Medical Bulletin. 2019. No. 2 (62). –pp.13-18
7. Therapeutic dentistry. Illness of the mucous membrane of an empty company / M.F. Danilevsky [ta insh.]. - K., 2010. - 640s. 5. Diseases of the oral mucosa / ed. L.M. Lukinykh. - N. Novgorod, 2003. - 210 p.].

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

4 ЖИЛД, 1 СОН

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ

ТОМ 4, НОМЕР 1

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 1

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Тадқиқот город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000